

BEARING RESPONSE OF FIBRE METAL LAMINATES CONSISTING OF GFRP AND WOVEN METALLIC FABRICS

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Keywords: Glass fibres, Hybrid composite, Resin-Transfer-Moulding

ABSTRACT

The subject of this work is the bearing response of fibre metal laminates (FML) consisting of glass fibre reinforced polymers (GFRP) and permeable woven metallic fabrics (WMF) using experimental methods. The hybrid composites are manufactured by using a single step vacuum assisted resin transfer moulding process (VARTM). Resulting in high quality composites for load introducing areas. The results are compared with quasi-isotropic GFRP composites.

The hybrid composites show a more ductile fracture behaviour in comparison to the quasi-isotropic GFRP laminate. With a metal volume fraction $V_f < 20$ vol.% a higher bearing strength is possible compared to GFRP. The permeable WMF increases the matrix flow through all layers in thickness direction while injection with the RTM-process. Furthermore, it yields to a weight reduction compared to solid metal plies.

1 INTRODUCTION

One of the big challenges in the field of fibre reinforced polymers (FRP) is to figure out a suitable way to introduce the mechanical load into the structure. In the aerospace industry and for rotor blades of wind turbines this is often realised by using bolted joints. In general, the load capacity of a bolted joint is enhanced by locally increasing the laminate thickness and corresponding ply drop-off to the nominal thickness (Fig. 1a).

Figure 1: Load capacity of a bolted joint, a) increased laminate thickness, b) with solid metal sheets, c) with permeable WMF.

However, this procedure increases the weight as well as causes secondary bending to the structure. An alternative to locally increase the laminate stress introducing capability is the replacement of single FRP layers with solid metal sheets (Fig. 1b). These sheets allow a two-dimensional load introduction into the laminate. Most of these fibre metal laminates are manufactured by using the prepreg-autoclave technology [1-5]. The metal volume fraction of these laminates is between 16-50 vol.-% metal [1, 5] and >50vol.-% metal [2]. It was shown that the local hybridisation increases the load capability of bolted joints [1, 2]. Both et al. [5] compared the results of pure CFRP laminates with CFRP/titanium

and CFRP/steel laminates using finite element analysis as well as experiments. The absolute bearing strengths increased significantly by substituting single CFRP-ply by thin metal sheets. However, the density specific values of pure CFRP were highest, followed by CFRP/titanium and CFRP/steel test results. Therefore a CFRP/metal laminate should only be considered if the thickness of the load instruction area must be of the similar thickness as the remaining part.

In this work the solid metal sheets are replaced by permeable woven metallic fabrics (Fig. 1c) of different architecture in order to allow a more cost-efficient process like resin transfer moulding (RTM). By using permeable metal layers the matrix can flow through all layers in thickness direction while the injection process. Consequently, all layers are equally wetted with the resin and show a void free microstructure. In addition, the permeable metal layers yield to a weight reduction compared to the solid metal sheets.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Material

The quasi-isotropic GFRP composite consists of unidirectional (UD) E-glass fibre (GF) non-crimp fabrics (NCF) ($q_F=528 \text{ g/m}^2$ in 0° -direction and $q_F=54 \text{ g/m}^2$ in 90° -direction) and biaxial ($\pm 45^\circ$) GF NCF ($q_F=430 \text{ g/m}^2$) (R&G Faserverbundwerkstoffe GmbH). For the hybrid composites the biaxial GF NCF are substituted by biaxial WMF (Haver&Boecker). The material, the volume fraction of a single layer and the weave of the different WMF is shown in

Table 1. The WMF are calendered, vapour degreased and cleaned by ultrasonic before applying.

WMF	Material	Weave	Volume fraction (%) of single ply
Al _{72%}	AlMg5	twill (2/2)	72
St _{39%}	X5CrNi18-10	plain	39
St _{72%}	X5CrNi18-10	twill (2/2)	72
St _{80%}	X5CrNi18-10	twill (4/4)	80

Table 1: WMF volume fraction of a single ply.

Figure 2 shows the structure and mass per unit area (q_F) of the used material for the quasi-isotropic GFRP and hybrid composites.

Figure 2: Light microscopy (LM) pictures of the different materials: a) UD-GF-NCF, b) biaxial GF NCF, c) Al_{72%} WMF, d) St_{39%} WMF, e) St_{72%} WMF, f) St_{80%} WMF.

Table 2 shows the lay-up of all laminates. The volume fraction (%) for the UD-GF-NCF and the different biaxial layers is given without the resin. For e.g. the GFRP/Al_{72%} hybrid consists out of 62 vol.-%. GF-NCF in 0°-direction, 6 vol.-%. GF-NCF in 90°-direction and 32 vol.-%. aluminium WMF in ±45°-direction.

Laminate	Lay-up	Volume fraction (%) of the plies in the laminate			
		GF		GF	WMF
		0°	90°	±45°	±45°
GFRP	$[\pm 45^{\circ}_{33\%}, (0^{\circ}_{61\%}, 90^{\circ}_{6\%})_2, \pm 45^{\circ}, (90^{\circ}, 0^{\circ})]_s$	61	6	33	-
GFRP/Al _{72%}	$[(Al_{\pm 45^{\circ}, 32\%})_2, (0^{\circ}_{62\%}, 90^{\circ}_{6\%})_2, (Al_{\pm 45^{\circ}})_2, (90^{\circ}, 0^{\circ})]_s$	62	6	-	32
GFRP/St _{39%}	$[(St_{\pm 45^{\circ}, 19\%})_2, (0^{\circ}_{73\%}, 90^{\circ}_{8\%})_2, (St_{\pm 45^{\circ}})_2, (90^{\circ}, 0^{\circ})]_s$	73	8	-	19
GFRP/St _{72%}	$[(St_{\pm 45^{\circ}, 29\%})_2, (0^{\circ}_{64\%}, 90^{\circ}_{7\%})_2, (St_{\pm 45^{\circ}})_2, (90^{\circ}, 0^{\circ})]_s$	64	7	-	29
GFRP/St _{80%}	$[(St_{\pm 45^{\circ}, 37\%})_2, (0^{\circ}_{57\%}, 90^{\circ}_{7\%})_2, (St_{\pm 45^{\circ}})_2, (90^{\circ}, 0^{\circ})]_s$	57	6	-	37

Table 2: Lay-up of the laminates.

For the injection procedure the resin RIMR 135 and the hardener RIMH 137 (Momentive Inc.) are used for all laminates [6]. During the RTM-process the laminates are cured in a mould (t=4 mm) at 60°C for 12 hours. After cutting and polishing the specimens are drilled (∅6.3H7) by one-shot-drilling with a hard metal-drill and a circumferential speed of $v_c=4000$ RPM. Afterwards all specimens are post cured at 80°C for 15 hours. To keep the specimens in constant condition the specimens are placed at least for 2 weeks in an exsiccator before testing allowing possible residual stresses to relax.

Figure 3 shows the LM micrographs of the cross section of the GFRP laminate and the hybrid GFRP/Al_{72%}. The GF are light grey, the resin dark grey and the WMF white. All composites show a high void free quality with no imperfections.

Figure 3: LM micrographs of the laminates: a) GFRP, b) GFRP/Al_{72%}.

The mean value of the glass transition temperature (T_g) of the laminates is measured by using the differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). For all laminates is $T_g = 93 \pm 2^{\circ}\text{C}$.

2.2 Experimental Methods

The bearing response testing is based on the ASTM D-5961-Procedure A [7], by using the double-shear tensile loading of the specimens with a single bolt (Figure 4). The fixture assembly is made from steel. The pin is made from 42CrMo4 steel ($\phi 6.3j6$) and causes a transition fit between pin and hole. The edge distance to pin diameter (e/d) and width to pin diameter (w/d) are experimental pre-tested to cause bearing failure for all laminates. The final geometries are width (w) = 36 mm and edge distance (e) = 26 mm.

Figure 4: Geometries of the specimen according to ASTM D5961-Procedure A [7].

The load-bearing test is performed in a universal tester Zwick 1474 with a maximum force of 100 kN. The head displacement rate is 2 mm/min. The video extensometer measures the displacement directly on the specimen surface. The load/displacement response is recorded until the load maximum is reached and finally has dropped down to 30 % from the maximum value.

3 RESULTS

Figure 5 shows representative the bearing stress-strain behaviour of the five different laminates. At least three specimens of each composite are tested. All specimens are failed by bearing. The bearing strength (σ_2) (2% hole expansion) and the maximum bearing stress (σ_{max}) of the hybrid GFRP/St_{80%} is highest compared to the values of the other laminates ($\sigma_2 = 424$ MPa, $\sigma_{max} = 491$ MPa). The maximum bearing strain to failure of the hybrid GFRP/St_{72%} and GFRP/St_{80%} is significantly higher in comparison to the laminates GFRP, GFRP/Al_{72%} and GFRP/St_{19%}. The Young's Modulus (E^{br}) is highest for the hybrid GFRP/St_{80%} ($E^{br} = 18.33$ GPa).

Figure 5: Bearing stress/strain diagram of the laminates.

The volume fraction V_f , density ρ , bearing strength and E-Modulus of the laminates are listed in Table 3. The volume fraction V_f is determined by DIN EN 2564 and is the basis to calculate the density values.

Laminate	Volume fraction			Laminate density ρ_{Laminate} (g/cm ³)	E-Modulus E^{br} [GPa]	Bearing strength σ_2 [MPa]
	V_f (%)					
	GF	Al	St			
GFRP	51.6	-	-	1.89	10.46±0.83	368.9±8.3
GFRP/Al _{72%}	32.7	14.3	-	1.84	9.01±0.70	331.2±8.7
GFRP/St _{39%}	32.8	-	5.6	2.00	7.87±0.92	307.3±5.8
GFRP/St _{72%}	32.1	-	12.5	2.51	9.65±0.75	352.8±2.6
GFRP/St _{80%}	31.9	-	19.0	2.91	17.64±0.54	424.1±4.9

Table 3: Volume fraction, density, bearing strength and Modulus of the laminates.

The failure behaviour of the composites is observed by LM directly after the 2% hole expansion. The GF are light grey, the resin dark grey, the WMF white and the debonded area black, respectively. The GFRP specimen in Figure 6 shows fibre failures, kink-bands and intralaminar cracking. Further loading of a similar specimen demonstrates that these failure modes increase. The GFRP specimens suddenly fail by delamination after a bearing strain of approximately 48 %.

Figure 6: GFRP specimen shortly after 2% hole expansion: a) sampling of the micrograph specimen, b) optical light microscopy.

Figure 7 shows a GFRP/Al_{72%} specimen. In some areas first aluminium fabric/matrix debonding occurs. The middle 0° GF layer shows a kink-band. In the other 0° GF layers first fibres start to buckle. By observing a similar specimen after further loading the previous failure modes increase and interlaminar cracking occurs. After a bearing strain of approximately 46 % the load has dropped down to 30 % from the maximum value.

Figure 7: GFRP/Al_{72%} specimen shortly after 2% hole expansion a) sampling of the micrograph specimen, b) optical light microscopy.

Figure 8 shows a GFRP/St_{39%} specimen. Stainless-steel fabric/matrix debonding occurs more distinct compared to the previous GFRP/Al_{72%} specimen. The 0° GF layers form kink-bands. Furthermore, in between the 0° GF layer and the WMF layer interlaminar delamination occurs. These failure modes increase by further loading. The load drop down to 56% of the maximum value after approximately 48% bearing strain.

Figure 8: GFRP/St_{39%} specimen shortly after 2% hole expansion a) sampling of the micrograph specimen, b) optical light microscopy.

Figure 9 shows a GFRP/St_{72%} specimen. Stainless-steel fabric/matrix debonding occurs less distinct compared to the previous GFRP/Al_{72%} specimen. However, this hybrid shows less distinct kink-bands in all 0° GF layers in comparison to the hybrid GFRP/Al_{72%}. By further loading a similar GFRP/St_{72%} specimen the previous failure modes increase and interlaminar cracking occur. After a bearing strain of approximately 120 % the load has still 56 % from the maximum value.

Figure 9: GFRP/St_{72%} specimen shortly after 2% hole expansion a) sampling of the micrograph specimen, b) optical light microscopy.

Figure 10 shows a GFRP/St_{80%} specimen. The failure modes are similar to the hybrid GFRP/St_{72%}. However, the stainless-steel fabric/matrix show much more debonding in comparison to the GFRP/St_{72%}.

Figure 10: GFRP/St_{80%} specimen shortly after 2% hole expansion a) sampling of the micrograph specimen, b) optical light microscopy.

4 DISCUSSION

The non-uniform distribution of the bearing pressure generates interlaminar shear stresses in the laminate, which causes fibre breakage and the formation of kink-bands in the 0°-GFRP layers. Fink et al. and Xia et al. observed this failure behaviour as well [1, 8]. The outer layers (mostly ±45°/90°) provide lateral support to the 0°-layers that reduce the stress concentration. In fact, it delay the initiation of fibre breaks, fibre buckling and delamination [9].

The experimental bearing response demonstrates that first fibre failure occur in the 0°-layer of the GFRP laminate at a stress level of approximately $\sigma^{br} = 300$ MPa (Figure 11b). The biaxial GFRP layers do not show failure modes at this point of loading. Consequently, the ±45°-layers still absorb the introduced stresses and the 0°-layers are less loaded within the linear-elastic area. Figure 6 shows

that after 2% hole expansion a kink-band and intralaminar cracking occur which leads under further loading to the failure of the composite.

In the hybrid GFRP/Al_{72%} first aluminium fabric/matrix debonding at approx. $\sigma^{br} = 300$ MPa occurs due to high stresses within the $\pm 45^\circ$ -aluminium layers (Figure 11c). Consequently, these layers start to deform plastically. This leads to early fibre buckling within the 0° GF layers compared to the GFRP laminate. Figure 7 shows that these effects increase at higher applied loading (after 2% hole expansion).

Figure 11d shows that first fibre breaks at approx. $\sigma^{br} = 300$ MPa occur in the 0° GF layers within the hybrid GFRP/St_{39%}. The biaxial layers do not show any debonding between the WMF and the matrix at this point of loading. This is caused by the coarse mesh size and the corresponding low stiffness of these WMF layers. The shear stresses are directly introduced in the 0° GF layers. Consequently, kink-bands and delamination occurs (Figure 8) and the hybrid GFRP/St_{39%} fails much early in comparison to the other hybrids.

The hybrid GFRP/St_{72%} shows a higher bearing strength, maximum bearing stress, Young's Modulus and bearing strain compared to the hybrid GFRP/Al_{72%} and GFRP/St_{39%} (Figure 5). Due to the higher stiffness of the WMF in comparison to the two previous hybrids the shear stresses are introduced into the hybrid by the biaxial WMF layers. Consequently, more WMF/matrix debonding at approx. $\sigma^{br} = 300$ MPa occur compared to the hybrid GFRP/Al_{72%}. In fact, the 0° GF layers are less loaded (Figure 11e).

The bearing strength, the maximum bearing stress and the Young's Modulus of the hybrid GFRP/St_{80%} is highest in comparison to the other laminates (Figure 5). The tightly WMF causes a high metal volume fraction and in fact a high stiffness for the single metal layer. The $\pm 45^\circ$ WMF layers carry the high shear stresses. Consequently, the 0° GF layers are less loaded in comparison to the other laminates and do not show any fibre failure at approx. $\sigma^{br} = 300$ MPa. Due to the high stresses in the biaxial layers the WMF/matrix debonding are more distinct at this point of loading compared to the other hybrids (Figure 11f).

Figure 11: Optical light microscopy at approx. $\sigma^{br} = 300$ MPa: a) sampling of the micrograph specimens, b) GFRP, c) GFRP/Al_{72%}, d) GFRP/St_{39%}, d) GFRP/St_{72%}, d) GFRP/St_{80%}.

The variation in the lay-up for the hybrid GFRP/St_{80%} compared to the other hybrids is caused by the higher thickness of the single WMF layer. Consequently, this hybrid consists of three WMF layers.

5 CONCLUSIONS

The permeable metal plies allow to manufacture high quality FRPs by RTM with enhanced load bearing capability. A metal volume fraction of $V_f = 19$ vol.% leads to a more ductile fracture behaviour and higher bearing strength (+15%) compared to conventional GFRP. Furthermore, it allows to keep the thickness of the load introduction area constant and no secondary bending of the laminate occurs.

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